

Use of E-Journals by Faculty Members and Research Scholars under N-List Programme

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Abstract

Internet revolution has led to the emergence of an e-generation era, where every aspect of life is taken online. So is the case with education, where internet has widened the horizon of learning. In the age of Information Technology, the traditional concept of acquiring information is gradually replaced by the accessing information online. In this context teaching faculty and research scholars demand online e-resources. With the growing popularity of e-resources, the traditional libraries are gradually focusing on e-journals and e-books. Keeping in mind the growing demand for e-resources, UGC has launched a project N-LIST that provides access to electronic journal and electronic books to eligible colleges. The present study is an effort to analyze the use of e-journals by faculty and researchers of higher education institutions in Puttur. The study reveals that the faculty and researchers are comfortable in using some of the electronic resources. However, there is a need to provide adequate training and infrastructure to teachers and researchers in using e-resources. It is seen that UGC-N-LIST is having a positive impact on academic and research activities in higher education institutions.

Key Words: Internet, E-journal, E-books, N-LIST, E-resources

Introduction

Internet revolution has led to the emergence of an e-generation era, where every aspect of life is taken online. So is the case with education, where internet has widened the horizon of learning. In the age of Information Technology, the traditional concept of acquiring information is gradually replaced by the accessing information online. In this context teaching faculty and research scholars demand online e-resources. Libraries are the lighthouse of information dissemination and are playing an important role in extending the required latest information quickly to their users. Due to insufficient funds libraries have been forced to cut on subscription for important journals. In order to provide current literature to Indian academia by covering the gap between the demand and supply through e-journals that can be subscribed online UGC has turned towards internet. In this connection UGC has established the Information and Library Network Centre (INFLIBNET) in 1991. The Centre acts as a nodal agency for networking of libraries and information centers in universities, institutions of higher learning with an aim to promote scholarly communication. The centre has taken up several new initiatives with an aim to keep abreast with trends and emerging technologies in information and communication. This includes N-LIST that provides access to electronic journals and electronic books to eligible colleges. The present paper is an attempt to study the use of E-journals Under N-LIST programme by the faculty and research scholars.

About N-LIST Programme:

A project entitled "National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content (N-LIST)" is jointly executed by the UGC-INFLIBNET Digital Library Consortium, INFILBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, IIT Delhi. This project was launched on 4th May 2010. The N-LIST project provides access to e-resources to students, researchers and faculty from colleges. The authorized users from colleges can access e-resources and download articles required by them. Only colleges accredited by the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) and those that have received 12B/2F certificate issued by the UGC are eligible to join this network. The registered member colleges are required to pay Rs.5000 as annual membership fee. As on June 2023, 3656 colleges all over India have joined this network.

Statement of problem

E-journals are made available with full text to meet requirement and expectation of academic and research community. So it is apt and essential to know how far faculty members, Ph.D. and M.Phil. scholars are making use of e-journals. Hence, the need is felt to study in detail the use of e-journals under N-LIST project by researchers and teachers. This present paper titled "**USE OF E-JOURNALS BY FACULTY MEMBERS AND RESEARCH SCHOLARS UNDER N-LIST PROGRAMME**" attempts to find the use of N-LIST e-journals by research scholars and academia of the colleges.

Objectives of the study:

The main purpose of the study reported here was to investigate the awareness, utilization

level of electronic information service. In the light of the aim of this study the following other research objectives of the study were set:

1. To identify the information needs of research scholars and faculty members at higher education institutions.
2. To be aware of the working of the N-LIST programme
3. To know the extent of the use of E-journals through N-LIST programme.
4. To ascertain the need for user orientation programme in accessing e-journals.
5. To know the significance of e-journals over print journals.
6. To know the degree of satisfaction derived by research scholars and teachers community while using e-journals

7. To identify the problems faced by the users in accessing e-journals and to suggest the ways and means for effective use of the N-LIST programme

Methodology:

Keeping in view the above objectives in mind, a structured questionnaire was prepared to collect data from the users of E-journals. For this purpose a total of 60 questionnaires were distributed among faculty members and researchers. Duly filled questionnaires were collected and then data was analyzed, tabulated, interpreted and presented through this paper.

Data Analysis:

Analysis of data is the ultimate step in research process. It is the link between raw data and significant results leading to conclusion. This process of analysis has to be result oriented.

Table1.1. Internet browsing skill of the respondents

Skill	No. of respondents(N=60)	Percentage
Adequate	30	50
Excellent	20	33.33
Poor	10	16.67

It is clear that 50% of the respondent have adequate skill in internet browsing while 33.33% are

excellent and 17.67% are poor in the skill of internet browsing.

Table1.2. Purpose of using E-journals

Purpose	No. of respondents(N=60)	Percentage
Research purpose	40	66.67
Academic purpose	30	50

Note: Respondents were permitted multiple answers E-journals are assisting a lot in research work. It is ascertained that 40(66.67%) go for using e-journals

for research purpose where as 30(50%) use it for their academic goal.

Table1.3. Reasons to use E-Journals

Reasons	No. of respondents(N=60)	Percentage
a). To become aware and keeping up-to-date in the subject field	30	50
b) For publishing Articles	10	16.67
c) To browse journals not available locally	10	16.67
d) For seminar presentation	15	25

Note: Respondents were permitted multiple answers There are varied reasons motivated to use e-journals as stated by the users under this study. Table 3 reveals that 30(50%) users look for e-journals ‘to become aware of the information relating to their

subject field, while10(16.67%) seek to obtain information for publishing articles, another 10(16.67%) browse the journals which are not locally available.15(25%) users require e-journals for preparing papers for seminar presentation.

Table1.4. Preferred methods of reading articles

Methods	No. of respondents(N=60)	Percentage
Reading articles available in printed form	40	66.67
Reading full text from the computer screen	20	33.33

The table 1.4 proclaims that 40(66.67%) and 20(33.33%) users follow the methods as priority ‘reading articles available in printed form’ and ‘reading from the computer screen’ respectively. As

per the views of respondents reading articles in printed form is more suitable and popular among the users rather than on screen.

Table 1.5. Frequency of using E-Journals through N-LIST programme

Frequency	No. of respondents(N=60)	percentage
Occasionally	15	25
2-3 times in a month	10	16.67%
Once in a week	25	41.67%
daily	10	16.67%

The Table1.5 reveals that 25(41.67%) users see the e-journals once in a week and 15(25%) occasionally, where as 10(16.67%) each use 2-3

times in a month and daily. It is proved to be good sign for acceptance of e-journals by the users of Vivekananda College.

Table 1.6. Access point of E-journals through N-LIST programme

Access point	No. of respondents	percentage
Central library	40	67.67
Department computer	20	33.33

It is clear from the above table that majority of respondents i.e. 40(67.67%) are accessing the e-journals from central library of the college and

20(33.33%) are accessing from their department computer.

Table1.7. Frequency of consulting librarian or other staff for help

Frequency	No. of respondents	percentage
Always	20	33.33
Sometimes	30	50
Rarely	10	16.67
Never	NIL	NIL

Summarizing the frequency of consulting the librarian or other library staff while using e-journals it is stated that 30(50%) users consult sometimes where as 20 (33.33%) and 10(16.67%) are

consulting the librarian or other library staff always and rarely respectively. There is no any user who has never consulted others for help.

Table1.8: Satisfaction of the users with time allotted for browsing

Factors	No. of respondents	percentage
Satisfied	25	41.67
Dissatisfied	35	58.33

It is ascertained from the table1.8 that 35(58.33%) are dissatisfied with the time allotted to them, but on the other hand 25(41.33%) found satisfied.

Table1.9. Common problems encountered during internet browsing

Problem area	No. of respondents	percentage
Limited number of terminals	25	41.67
Slow internet connectivity	10	16.67
Frequent power failure	5	8.33
Insufficient printing facilities	20	33.33

It was realised that access to electronic resources was hindered by some of the common problems which need to be viewed intensively by the librarian. With regard to these difficulties Table 1.9 explores that 25(41.67%) respondents said that the number of PCs are insufficient, where as

20(33.33%) users have said that there are no sufficient printing facilities to take print out of articles from the computer. A small portion of respondents i.e., 8.33% said that they encounter the problem of power failure where as 16.67% of users face the problem of slow internet connectivity

Table1.10. Evaluation of N-LIST programme

Particulars	No. of respondents	percentage
Excellent	13	21.67
Very Good	22	36.67
Good	20	33.33
Fair	5	8.33
Poor	NIL	NIL

The data explored in the table 1.10, reveals that 13(21.67%) users remarked excellent and 22(36.67%) said very good and further 20(33.33%) rated it as good and 5(8.33%) said that it is fair. However none of them rank the programme as 'Poor' which is a good sign for the UGC-N-LIST programme as a whole

Major Findings of the survey

On the basis of the above analysis and observations, it is the overall feeling that e-journals have been a success for the users in higher education institutions. Further, looking after the rapidly growing trend of e-resources the researchers and faculty members should be encouraged to use UGC N-LIST e-resources for their academic and research purposes rather than to rely on printed sources alone. Following are the major findings of the survey.

1. 50% users possess adequate internet browsing skill, while only 16.67% found poor.
2. Majority of respondents (66.67%) are more concerned about the use of e-resources for their research purpose.
3. The survey attests the most vital reasons which motivated the users for using e-resources are to become aware and keeping up-to-date in the subject field (50%)
4. Reading articles available in printed form is highly appreciated by maximum (66.67%) users other than reading from computer screen.
5. A large number of (41.67%) users use e-resources once in a week
6. 66.67% users access e-resources from the central library
7. 50% users consult 'sometimes' followed by 16.67% rarely while 33.33% consult always whenever they look for any information over internet in library.
8. 58.33% Library e-users have shown their dissatisfaction with the time allotted to them for browsing in computer laboratory.
9. Insufficient Computers (41.67%) and insufficient printing facilities(33.33%) are the common problems mostly faced by the users
10. In view point of 36.67% of users, N-LIST E-resources is very good

Suggestions:

In the present study, a feedback technique adopted through this survey to find out the working of the system of e-resources and services rendered by libraries of higher education institutions. The feasible and practicable suggestions are enumerated as under:

1. Provision for more PCs and extension of Library Computer Laboratory for better use of e-journals are needed.

2. The required training should be provided to research scholars, teachers as well as students for huge and optimum use of e-resources.
3. Proper internet facility should be provided in the central library.
4. Users should be facilitated for print outs pages by the library whenever they need with minimum payment system.
5. Additional power supply system must be functional as quickly as possible and should be available for all time to cope up accidental power failure.
6. Faculty members must be encouraged to use e-resources for academic purpose also.

Conclusion:

Faculty and researchers in higher education institutions are computer literate and comfortable in using some of the electronic resources. However, it is necessary to increase the awareness of the existence of other search tools. There is a need to provide adequate training to teachers and researchers in using e-resources. It is seen that UGC-N-LIST is having a positive impact and facilitates the faculties to undertake research work.

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